

G7 COUNTRIES OR G7 FINANCIAL INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *The countries of the world are creating various organizations depending on their place. In particular, the UN (United Nation), ShCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization), CIC (Cooperation of Independent Countries), NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization). Today's article is about the famous Great Seven countries and their history and financial freedom. Which countries are included in these organization? These countries are Great Britain, Germany, Italy, Canada, USA, France and Japan. Among these countries, one can also see the countries that were in a big financial crisis at the time, especially Germany was in a difficult situation after the Second World War, Japan went through the crisis after the atomic bomb was dropped. In this article, we will get to know the specific information about each country.*

Keywords: *state, economy, industry, size, world, finance, history, production.*

The "Great Seven" is an unofficial international club that unites Great Britain, Germany, Italy, Canada, France, Japan and the USA. The unofficial forum of the leaders of these countries (with the participation of the European Commission) also has the same name, and approaches to current international problems are agreed upon within the summit. According to an unwritten rule, group summits are traditionally held annually in each member state in turn. The G7 is not an international organization, it is not based on an international agreement, it has no charter and secretariat. G7 decisions are not binding. Since G7 does not have a charter, it is not possible to officially accept the status of a member of this institution. The idea of holding meetings of leaders of economically developed countries appeared in the early 1970s. This was caused by the economic crisis and the inability of the USA, Western Europe and Japan to agree on economic and financial issues. held in the palace. The heads of state and prime ministers of France, USA, Great Britain, Germany, Italy and Japan gathered in it. In 1976, the "six" became the "seven" when Canada joined. In 1991-2002, the stage gradually became "eight" with the participation of Russia. In 2014, Russia was expelled from the G8 after annexing Crimea, which belongs to Ukraine. Government leaders are participating in the annual summit of G7 leaders. The member state holding the G7 presidency is responsible for organizing and holding the annual summit. Successive annual summits can be analyzed chronologically in controversial ways, including the sequence of host countries for the summits repeated in time and sequence. In general, each country holds the summit once every 7 years.

The last 48th summit is planned for 2022 in Germany, the 49th summit in Japan in 2023, and the 50th summit in Italy in 2024. For information, the first summit was held in France on November 15-17, 1975, and this summit was G6.

1. **Great Britain-** (English: Great Britain) or the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (English: United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland) is a country in North-Western Europe. It is located on the island of Great Britain (90% of the country's territory is on this island) and the northeastern part of the island of Ireland, as well as small islands adjacent to them (Anglesey, White, Normandy, Orkney, Hebrides, Shetland, etc.). It is surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean from the west and the North Sea from the east. Great Britain is often called England after the main part of the country. The area is 244.1 thousand km². Population 68,081 million] people (2020). The capital is the city of London. It consists of 4 administrative and political parts (England, Wales, Scotland and neighboring islands, Northern Ireland) that are historically formed and nationally different. The Isle of Man and the Channel Islands are an independent administrative territory.

Great Britain is a constitutional monarchy. The head of state is the king (queen). The country has no constitution. The Great Liberties Act 1215, the Habeas Corpus Act 1679, the Statute of Westminster 1931, the Representation of the People Act 1969 and other important parliamentary acts. Legislative power is exercised by the king (queen) and parliament (it consists of two chambers: the House of Lords and the House of Commons), and the executive power is exercised by the government (cabinet) headed by the prime minister. The prime minister is appointed by the king (queen). Members of the government must be members of parliament. England, Wales and Scotland within the United Kingdom have their own judicial system and local government bodies. Northern Ireland has administrative autonomy and is governed by a Governor appointed by the King (Queen). Great Britain heads the Commonwealth of Nations, which unites countries and territories that were formerly part of the British Empire. Industry accounts for 90% of UK exports. After the Second World War, major changes took place in the industrial structure: the share of sectors such as mining, ferrous metallurgy, light and food industry, as well as shipbuilding and automobile industry decreased; the share of energy, electrical engineering and chemical industry increased.

Atomic, electronic, aerospace, oil refining and petrochemical industries have gained great importance. Mechanical engineering is an important branch of industry, the production of automobiles, airplanes, rockets, ships, complex equipment for industrial workplaces, scientific apparatus and instruments, radio electronics and electronic products is especially distinguished. Tractor manufacturing, machine tool manufacturing, oil refining, chemical (plastic and synthetic

tars, medicines, mineral fertilizers, dyes, chemical fibers, synthetic rubber, sulfuric acid production), textile, food industries are developed. There are large factories for shoemaking, tailoring and other branches of light industry. Most of the engineering centers are located in Southern and Central England, the most important of which are in London, Birmingham, Coventry, Luton, and Sheffield. The main centers of metallurgy are in South Wales, Yorkshire and Humberside, Northern England and Scotland. Non-ferrous metallurgical works in the Midlands, South Wales, Tyneside and London. Nuclear power plants are located around North West England and London. Chemical industry sites in Greater London, Lancashire, Cheshire, North Sea and Bristol Bay coasts, textile industry sites in Lancashire and Yorkshire. There are large oil and gas reserves in the North Sea. In the United Kingdom, an average of 48.2 mln. tons of coal, 121.8 mln. tons of oil, 89.8 bln. m³ of natural gas is extracted, 304.5 bln. kWh of electricity is generated (mainly in thermal power plants), 17.5 mln. tons of steel are produced. Only 2% of the working population of the country is employed in agriculture. Agriculture in the United Kingdom is characterized by a high level of intensity, productivity and mechanization. It provides 75% of the country's food needs. The main branch of the United Kingdom is cattle breeding. 12 million in the United Kingdom. cattle, 7.5 mln. pigs, 41.5 mln. sheep, 131 mln. there is a bird. The main crop in agriculture is grain. Sugar beets and potatoes are also planted. Vegetable growing, horticulture, and flower growing are developed. Fish is caught in the North Sea and Atlantic Ocean.

2. Germany (German: Deutschland), the Federal Republic of Germany (German: Bundesrepublik Deutschland) is a country in Central Europe. It is located on the coast of the Northern Baltic Sea. The area is 357 thousand km². Population 83,149,300 (as of 2019).[1] The capital is the city of Berlin. Administratively, it is divided into 16 regions (states), regions into districts, districts into districts, districts into communities.

GFR is a federal republic. Its current constitution was adopted on May 23, 1949, and amendments were made to it in 1954, 1956, 1990, 1993, and 1994. The head of state is the federal president. He is elected by a specially convened federal assembly for a term of 5 years and can be re-elected only once. The Federal Assembly is convened by the President of the Bundestag and consists of Bundestag deputies and members elected by the Landtags (land parliaments). If the president becomes incapacitated or dies, the chairman of the Bundesrat performs the powers of the president. Legislative power is exercised by the parliament. It consists of two chambers: Bundestag and Bundesrat. The Bundestag is elected by the population for a period of 4 years. The Bundesrat

consists of representatives appointed by the state governments from among themselves for a period of 4 years. Executive power is vested in the federal government headed by the federal chancellor. The Federal Chancellor is elected by a majority vote in the Bundestag on the proposal of the President. Ministers are appointed by the president on the proposal of the federal chancellor. Each country has its own constitution, parliament and government.

Mechanical engineering is the backbone of the German economy. Brown coal (first place in the world), hard coal, oil, natural gas, polymetallic ores, potash and ashtuzi are mined. Power engineering, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, mechanical engineering, shipbuilding, chemistry and petrochemicals, woodworking, food industry, china industry are highly developed. German industry consists mainly of medium-sized enterprises. More than 32% of all employees in industry (2.2 million people) work in large firms. Siemens concern, automotive companies such as Volkswagen, BMW and Daimler Benz, chemical concerns such as Hoechst, Bayer and BASF, coal mining company Rurkole AG, electrical engineering concern FEBA and RVE. or "Bosh" group is known all over the world and has branches, enterprises or research institutions all over the world. Large companies are mostly customers of small and medium-sized enterprises. The decisive factor in these successes was the transition from a controlled economy to a market economy in 1948. The main industries are vehicle manufacturing, mechanical engineering, chemical industry, electrical engineering, food, metallurgy, mining, precision mechanics and optics, aviation and space industry. In the field of technical development, German industry occupies one of the leading positions in the world. Thanks to the use of high technologies, Germany's economy is a world leader in the production of pharmaceutical products, the latest organic chemicals and artificial materials, medical electronics, optics and measuring instruments, the creation of new cars and machinery, telecommunications, and environmental protection technologies. Handicrafts with a long and beautiful tradition have developed in Germany.

3. Italy- (Italia), Republic of Italy (Repubblica Italiana) is a country located in the south of Europe, in the Mediterranean basin. The Apennine Peninsula included Sicily, Sardinia and other small islands. The area is 301.2 thousand km². The population is 60.92 million. person (2012). Administratively, it is divided into 20 regions. The capital is the city of Rome.

The current constitution was adopted on December 22, 1947 and entered into force on January 1, 1948. The head of state is the president (since May 1999 K. A. Champi). He is elected for a period of 7 years at the joint meeting of both chambers of the parliament with the participation of the representatives of the regions. The legislative body is the Parliament consisting of the Chamber of Deputies and the Senate. Executive power is exercised by the Council of Ministers.

The President is the Chairman of the Council of Ministers and appoints ministers upon his proposal.

Italy is a highly developed industrial-agrarian country. One of the 10 most developed countries in the world. The share of industry in the gross domestic product is 31.6%, the share of agriculture is 2.9%, and the share of services is 65.5% (1997). In Italy, more than 12 million people work in the service sector, 6.5 million. people in industry, 1.5 mln. the person is employed in agriculture.

Industry is dominated by heavy industry. In particular, mechanical engineering, metallurgy, automobile engineering, textiles, electric power, oil refining, and petrochemicals are developed. A large part of industrial products is exported. Italy has few reserves of raw materials and energy, and those that do exist are unevenly distributed. Oil and gas (mainly in the Padan plain, foothills of the Po River, areas near the coast of the Adriatic Sea and in Sicily), lead, tin, zinc (mainly in Sardinia), iron ores (in Aosta and Sardinia), bauxite, cinnabar (mercury ore), pyrite (in the Tuscany region), sulfur, salt (in Sicily), brown coal, building materials, etc. is mined. Thermal power plants are the basis of electric energy. Nuclear power plants and geothermal stations were built. An average of 222 billion per year. kWh of electricity is generated. The metallurgical industry mainly operates on the basis of imported raw materials. The largest enterprises of ferrous metallurgy are located around Genoa, Naples, as well as in Pombino and Taranto; non-ferrous metallurgical enterprises are located in the cities of Venice, Bolzano, Mori, Milan and Sardinia. Oil refineries (based on imported raw materials) are located mainly in coastal areas (Genoa, Naples, Venice, Spezia, Augusta) and in cities where oil products are used the most (Milan, etc.). Machine-building networks, which are the leading branches of industry: automotive (Turin), shipbuilding (Genoa, Livorno, Naples, Venice, Trieste), machine tools (Milan, Brescia, Turin), equipment (Ivrea), electrical engineering (Milan, Varese, Bergamo, Turin, Genoa) and electronics (around Milan) industry is developed. The production of petrochemicals, plastics, mineral fertilizers, artificial fibers, pharmaceuticals and rubber products, and synthetic rubber has reached a high level. Lombardy and Piedmont are traditional textile centers. The main branches of the food industry are production of flour, macaroni, cheese, sugar, canned food, olive oil, grape wine (70 million hectoliters per year). Light industry, in particular, shoe production, has developed. Special attention is paid to craftsmanship.

The leading branches of agriculture are agriculture (58%) and animal husbandry (42%). 34.3% of the fertile land (19.6 million hectares) is plowed and cultivated, 11% is garden, vineyard and orchard, 19.2% is lawn and pasture. The main grain crops are wheat, corn, oats, barley, rice. Sugar beets, grapes, olives, citrus fruits and vegetables are also grown. Italy is one of the world's leading producers of wine. 6 million per year in Italy. produces about tons of various wet fruits, about 60% of which are grown in specialized farms in the north of the country. There are many almond, walnut and hazelnut orchards in the southern regions. Grape harvest is 10 million per year. tons (90% of it is processed and made into wine), 3.3 million tons of citrus fruits per year. tons, tomato harvest 5.5 mln. tons. Cattle (8.8 million heads), pigs (9.6 million heads) and sheep (12.2 million heads) are raised as livestock. In the north of the country, dairy and meat breeding is predominant. Fishing is well developed.

4. Canada is a member of the UN and NATO and has signed an agreement with the United States on "Free Economic Trade". Dominion of the United Kingdom. Sovereign right was granted in 1931. However, independence was not declared. The country is governed by a Governor-

General appointed by the King (or Queen) of the United Kingdom. The population is 38.3 million person (year 2021)

Canada is a federal state within the Commonwealth of Great Britain. The current Constitution entered into force on April 17, 1982. The head of state is the King (Queen) of Great Britain, on whose behalf the Governor-General governs the country. The Queen appoints the Governor General on the recommendation of the Prime Minister of Canada, usually for a 5-year term. Legislative power is exercised on behalf of the Queen by the Governor-General and a bicameral Parliament (the Senate and the House of Commons). Executive power is exercised on behalf of the Queen by a government consisting of the Governor-General and the Prime Minister and Ministers (prime minister since 1993, Jean Chrétien). The official currency is the Canadian dollar.

Canada's fiscal policy is set by the Government of Canada when it presents its annual budget to the House of Commons. These policies affect the economy through government subsidies and incentives. In addition, fiscal policy sets rates for income taxes, sales taxes, excise taxes, and other forms of revenue for the Canadian government.

Monetary policy in Canada is governed by the Bank of Canada, which affects short-term % rates by announcing daily upward or downward changes in its interest rate or refinancing rate. By changing the refinancing rate in this way, the Bank of Canada maintains control over all other interest rates, such as mortgage rates, etc. In addition, this exposure to rates may result from changes in the exchange rate of the Canadian dollar.

The Bank of Canada aims to keep inflation at an estimated 2%, the midpoint of its target range of 1% to 3%. Although inflation control measures are based on the global CPI, the Bank uses a benchmark index to calculate trend inflation and guide its policies. The growth rate of this index provides a more reliable measure of the underlying trend of inflation and is the best indicator of future changes in the world CPI" (Bank of Canada Pages[1]).

The consumer price index (world CPI) is an "indicator of price changes obtained by comparing the retail prices of goods and services" of a basket of goods "published by Statistics Canada and normalized for two different dates."

The benchmark index is "a type of consumer price index, which includes the eight most volatile components (fruits, vegetables, gasoline, fuel oil, natural gas, mortgage interest, urban transport and tobacco - 16% of the CPI basket) and other components of changes in indirect taxes

(Until May 2001, the Bank of Canada used the CPI as a reference index without the effects of changes in food, energy and indirect taxes)" (Bank of Canada pages).

5. USA- (USA; English: United States of America, USA), United States (English: United States) or simply America (English: America) is a country in North America. Its capital is Washington, a member of the United Nations. The USA is surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean to the east, the Pacific Ocean to the west, and the Gulf of Mexico to the southeast. Administratively, it is divided into 50 states and one federal district. The states of Alaska and Hawaii are located outside the main territory of the country. The Commonwealth of Puerto Rico, the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands, Guam, the Virgin Islands, and American Samoa also belong to the United States. Its area is 9.8 million km². Its population is more than 331 million people, and it is the third most populous country in the world.

The United States is a federal republic consisting of 50 states, one federal district, and five territories.[6][7][8] In addition, it is the oldest existing federation in the world. In 2021, the United States ranked 26th in the Democracy Index.[9]

The current US constitution was adopted in 1787. The head of the state and government, the commander-in-chief of the armed forces is the president, his powers are enormous. Together with the vice-president, he is elected for a period of 4 years by indirect, two-stage elections (through the electoral commission). Legislative power is exercised by a bicameral congress consisting of a senate and a house of representatives. The Senate has 100 senators (they are elected for 6-year terms, 2 from each state, and 1/3 is renewed every 2 years). 435 deputies are elected to the House of Representatives for 2 years. The executive branch is the US government appointed by the president with the consent of the senate; It will consist of 13 ministers. The government is not accountable to Congress. Each state has its own constitution. The legislative power in the state is exercised by the legislative assembly, and the executive power is exercised by the governor. The constitutional system of the US state is based on three political and legal rules, which are the separation of powers, federalism, and constitutional control of the court. The principle of separation of powers envisages the independence of the three branches of state power - the legislative, executive and judicial authorities, and the demarcation of tasks between them. The three branches at the federal level are Congress, the President, and the Supreme Court.

The Industrial Recovery Act, enacted on June 16, 1933, was another important New Direction event. This law was introduced by the state of the industry. As a result of the First World War, the United States becomes the leading country in the world. American companies supplied European countries with military equipment, weapons and food in huge quantities and at high prices. Many European countries received loans from the USA to fight the war, and after the war

they became indebted to the USA. dollar profit. On May 12, 1933, the Law on Assistance to Farmers was passed. It was necessary to increase the prices of their products. Farmers were offered to conclude a contract with the state to reduce the area of cultivated fields and the type of livestock. They were awarded for this. Farmers' debts were taken over by the state and suspended for an indefinite period. The state gave loans to hundreds of thousands of farmers. Non-profitable farms were liquidated. "New direction" has made a significant shift in the field of social legislation to liberalize social relations in the United States. In 1935, the US Congress passed the "Wagner Act". According to this law, workers had the right to conclude collective agreements and the right to strike. The recognition of the rights of trade unions and the right to strike gave a new impetus to the struggle of the working class for the unity of its ranks. The number of trade unions began to increase. Along with the recognized center, the American Federation of Labor, a new trade union organization, the Committee of Manufacturing Trade Unions, appeared. This organization was named the Congress of Industrial Trade Unions in 1938. During Roosevelt's presidency, the liberalization of domestic policy was also reflected in foreign policy. US foreign policy has become more flexible and fair. The first major foreign policy work of the new administration was the establishment of diplomatic relations with the Soviet Union in November 1933. The normalization of relations between the two countries has intensified their economic relations. In 1935 and 1937, a trade agreement was signed between the USA and the USSR, which allowed the development of mutually beneficial economic relations between the two countries. In his speech in Chicago on October 5, 1937, Roosevelt called for a quarantine around the aggressors. He also strongly condemned the actions of the fascist states. On July 26, 1939, the United States canceled the trade agreement with Japan. After the outbreak of World War II on November 4, 1939, the Neutrality Act was revised, allowing Britain and France to purchase arms from the United States.

66.3% of US national income is generated in industry. About half of industrial production is in the hands of industrial corporations. Among them: Exxon, Mobil, Texaco, Chevron, Standard Oil of California, Standard Oil of Indiana, Gulf Oil, General Motors, Ford Motor Company, "Chrysler" car, "IBM", "General Electric", "ITT" electrical engineering, "YU. Steel foundry, Dupont de Nemours chemical and other corporations. "General Dynamics", "Lockheed", "McDonnell Douglas", "Grumman", "Hughes Aircraft" take the leading place among military industrial corporations. Aviation-rocket-space, power engineering, electronic, as well as petrochemical, atomic and energy industries are developing very quickly. 74% of electricity is produced in thermal power plants, 12.1% in hydroelectric power plants, 14.1% in NPPs. Oil (Gulf,

California, Alaska), natural gas and sulfur (Gulf), coal (Appalachian and Central Basins), iron ore (Lake Superior area), phosphorite (Florida), uranium, non-ferrous metals, potassium salts, etc. .k. is mined. The main centers of ferrous metallurgy are Chicago, Pittsburgh, Detroit, Cleveland, Buffalo, Baltimore, Philadelphia. The aluminum industry is located around the Gulf and in the Columbia and Tennessee river basins. The leading branch of industry is machine-building and metallurgy. The production of industrial and energy equipment, construction and agricultural machinery is mainly located in the northeastern states, and the production of electrical engineering and communication equipment is located in the northeast and California. The main center of automobile industry is Detroit. Aircraft, rocket and space equipment manufacturing plants are mainly located in Los Angeles, San Diego, Boston, New York, Philadelphia, Baltimore, Buffalo, Dallas, Atlanta and other cities. Shipbuilding (mainly military shipbuilding) developed in the ports of the northeastern coast of the United States. The main centers of nuclear industry are Oak Ridge, Paducah, Portsmouth, Aiken, Hanford. The chemical industry produces chemicals, plastics, chemical fiber, synthetic rubber, varnishes, detergents, paints, mineral fertilizers, etc. These chain enterprises are located mainly in northeastern states, in cities along the coast of the Gulf of Mexico. The military industry is mainly in California, New York, Texas, Connecticut, Missouri, Massachusetts, Virginia. The most important light industries are textiles (more in North Carolina, South Carolina, and Georgia) and clothing (New York and southern states). The leather-shoe industry is well developed. The food industry is well supplied with its raw materials. Its leading industries are meat, milk, flour, oil, sugar, canned goods, alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages, tobacco.

6. France - the official name of the Republic of France (French: République française)[5] is a country in Western Europe. It is surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean and the English Channel to the west and north, and the Mediterranean Sea to the south. The area is 547.03 thousand km². The population is 67.5 million people (2021). The capital is the city of Paris. Administratively, it is divided into 22 regions (provinces), 96 departments. France includes overseas departments (Guadeloupe, Martinique, Guiana, Reunion), overseas territories (Tahiti, New Caledonia, French Polynesia, Wallis and Futuna Islands in the Pacific Ocean, etc.), territorial units (Mayotte and Saint-Pierre and Miquelon).

France is a republic, historically there was a khanate. The current constitution was adopted in a referendum in 1958 (amended several times). The head of state is the president. He is elected by general and direct voting for a term of 5 years and can be re-elected once more. Legislature - Parliament consists of 2 houses (National Assembly and Senate). Executive power is exercised by the president and the Council of Ministers (government).

France ranks 4th in the world in terms of industrial production after the USA, Japan and Germany. Main production sectors: aerospace industry, mechanical engineering (aircraft, shipbuilding), electronic equipment, radio electronics, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, chemical and pharmaceutical products, textiles, tailoring, oil refining, petrochemicals, etc. In France, iron ore (mainly in Lorraine), uranium ore (LaCruzy, L'Ecarpierre and other mines), bauxite (in the Var and Ero departments) and aluminum ore are mined. Lorraine is a traditional center of idol production. In the following period, idol mining in the center and south of the country decreased somewhat. Nickel, potassium salts, gypsum, tungsten and sulfur, barium, kaolin, asbestos, feldspar, a small amount of lead, pyx and silver are mined. Landes, a southwestern region of France, has oil and gas reserves. Steel (LeCryozeau, Saint-Etienne), aluminum (Gardann,

Salendre, Noger), copper (LePale), lead and zinc (Nouayel Godot, Lyon, Vivier), nickel (Le Havre), cobalt, tungsten and others are melted in metallurgical plants. Construction materials, including sand, gravel, and stone, are mined throughout France. Renault and Peugeot are the largest car manufacturers. The centers of the automobile industry are located in Paris, Montbéliard, Lyon. The main centers of aerospace industries (military and civil aircraft, helicopters, engines, rockets and space equipment) are Paris, Toulouse, Bordeaux. Shipbuilding developed (Nantes, Dunkirk, Marseilles). Locomotives and wagons, machine tools, tractors, agricultural machines and others are produced. French companies are known for their latest technologies in defense, transport engineering and other sectors. An average of 475.6 billion per year. kWh of electricity (3/4 of which is generated in nuclear power plants). The main centers of the atomic industry are LeBuche, Pierrelat, Markul. The oil and petrochemical industry produces plastics, synthetic rubber and tar, chemical fiber, military chemical products, mineral fertilizers, pharmaceuticals, chemicals and other products (Paris, Lyon, Le Havre and Marseille). The main branch of the light industry is textiles, and there are large yarn, wool, linen, jute, and knitting enterprises in Paris, Lille, Armantier, Roubeux-Turquen, Mulhouse, Epinal, and Troyes. The textile and haberdashery, footwear, and food industries are developed. Cognac, wine, liqueur, champagne are famous in the world.

7.Yaponiya- Sharqiy [Osiyoda](#), [Tinch okeanidagi](#) orollarda joylashgan davlat. . Yaponiya hududida 6,8 mingga yaqin orol bo‘lib, shimoli-sharqdan janubi-g‘arbga qariyb 9.13 ming kmga cho‘zilgan;Yaponiyaning eng yirik 4ta orollari: Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku va Kyushu. Yaponiyaning tabiiy boyliklari deyarli juda kam davlatning atrofini tinch okean o‘rab turganligi tufayli mamlakatning tuprog‘ida [yod](#) moddasi yetarlicha hisoblanadi. Shimolidan [Oxota dengizi](#), sharq va janubi-sharqdan Tinch okean, g‘arbdan Yapon va Sharqiy Xitoy dengizlari bilan o‘ralgan. Maydon 377,8 ming km². Aholisi 126 mln. kishi (2021). Poytaxti — [Tokio](#) shahri. Yaponiya ma‘muriy jihatdan 47 prefekturaga bo‘linadi. [Shinkansen] yaponiyaning eng Tez yurar poyezdi hisoblanadi. [Japan Air Lines] bu yaponiya havo yollari JAL deb hisoblanadi.

Agricultural land makes up 35.6% of the country's territory, of which 40% is pasture and hayfield. Animal husbandry is the leading branch of agriculture (55% of production value). Cattle, sheep, pigs, and poultry are raised. Wheat, the main agricultural crop, is grown in the lowlands of Northern France. Barley and corn are of great importance. Rye is grown in the barren lands of the Central France massif, and rice is grown in the Rhône delta. Among technical crops, sugar beet, flax, hops and tobacco take an important place. Vineyards occupy a large area in the department of Bordeaux and in the valleys of Rhône, Saône, Garonne, Dordogne and Loire Valley. Vegetable growing, horticulture, and flower growing are developed. Wood is made in forests. Fish is caught in the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea.

7. Japan is a country located in East Asia, on the islands of the Pacific Ocean. . There are about 6,800 islands in the territory of Japan, stretching from northeast to southwest for about 9,1300 km; the 4 largest islands of Japan are: Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku and Kyushu. Japan's natural resources are very few, due to the fact that the country is surrounded by the Pacific Ocean, iodine is sufficient in the country's soil. It is surrounded by the Sea of Okhotsk from the north, the Pacific Ocean from the east and southeast, and the Japanese and East China seas from the west. The area is 377.8 thousand km². The population is 126 million. person (2021). The capital is Tokyo. Administratively, Japan is divided into 47 prefectures. [Shinkansen] is the fastest train in Japan. [Japan Air Lines] is the Japanese airline JAL.

Japan is a constitutional monarchy. The current ban came into effect on May 3, 1947 (with subsequent amendments). The head of state is the emperor (Akihito since 1989). According to Article 1 of the Constitution, it is "a symbol of the unity of the state and people." Land members of the imperial family are heirs to the imperial throne. According to the constitution, the emperor has no independent power. All activities of the Emperor in relation to state affairs are carried out with the advice and approval of the Cabinet. The supreme legislative power is exercised by the 2-chambered parliament (House of Representatives and the House of Councilors), and the executive power is exercised by the government headed by the Prime Minister (Cabinet of Ministers). Japanese industry is one of the most developed and advanced sectors in the world economy; among the leaders of the world economy are Japan's Toyota Motors, Matsushita Electric, Sony Corporation, Honda Motors, Toshiba, Fujitsu and other companies are included. Small and medium-sized businesses play a significant role in the automotive, electronics and electrical engineering industries. The main structural factor is science and education, so special attention is paid to them. Japan is a country located in the eastern part of the Eurasian continent. The total area is 378,000 sq. km. The country consists of four main islands - Honshu, Hokkaido, Kyushu, Shikoku and more than 6,800 smaller islands. Japan has the leading economy among the world countries, its share in the world GDP is 6.2 percent. In the world economy, the growth rate of Japan's economy is decreasing due to the strengthening of the integration of the PRC and other developing countries into the world economy. Medium and small businesses are operating effectively in all areas. It is the main element of the market in the development of competition, increasing the competitiveness of goods. 99% of Japanese companies are small and medium-sized businesses. It plays a major role in the automotive, electronic and electrical engineering industries. Export composition: vehicles, cars, motorcycles, electronics, electrical engineering, etc. Imports include: [machinery]] and equipment, fuel, food, raw materials, etc.

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